

Standardization of formulated products of mancozeb by EDTA method

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EDTA volumetric method has been successfully used for the standardization of mancozeb formulation using ammonia buffer (pH 10) and Eriochrome black T as internal indicator.

Mancozeb is a protective leaf-fungicide¹. In order to fulfil the primary purpose of fungicidal effect and to minimize any adverse effect, it is essential to develop proper testing procedures for mancozeb.

The analytical methods used so far are based on the estimation of carbon disulphide², by using spectrophotometry^{3,4} and gas chromatography^{5,6}. These methods are very sensitive and accurate but are laborious, time-consuming and non-selective. The present communication deals with the volumetric determination of mancozeb to a visual end-point with ethylenediamine tetraacetic acid (EDTA) using Eriochrome black T at pH 10.

Results and Discussion

Preliminary experiments on the dissolution of mancozeb indicates that on treating dust formulations (1 g) of mancozeb with 100 ml of 1 M sodium hydroxide a turbid solution containing brown precipitate is formed. The dust (2.25 g) is soluble in ammonia buffer (10 ml) of pH 10. The mancozeb solution is also prepared by treating aqueous suspension of the mancozeb dust with cation exchanger resins in ammonium form.

Literature survey shows that mancozeb is insoluble in most of the organic solvents and very slightly soluble in water¹. Standard solution of mancozeb can be prepared in 0.1 M aqueous EDTA⁵. Mancozeb has also been found

soluble⁷ in aqueous alkaline 0.2 M EDTA containing L-cystine. Alkali metal and ammonium salts of alkali dithiocarbamic acids are water-soluble⁸. The versenate complexometric titrations⁹ are simple, inexpensive and quick for estimating metal ions. However, EDTA titrations have not been tried to determine metal ion in pesticides. Therefore, this procedure has been utilized for the determination of zinc and manganese in mancozeb.

The quantitative data of mancozeb, zineb and maneb obtained by versenate titrations are recorded in Tables 1-4. The mancozeb concentration can be obtained either by using the calibration curve (plot of volume of versenate consumed versus mancozeb concentration) or by using the following expressions :

$$x \mu\text{g of zineb} = \frac{65.38}{275.74} \times x \mu\text{g of Zn}$$

$$y \mu\text{g of maneb} = \frac{54.94}{265.29} \times y \mu\text{g of Mn}$$

$$\text{Mancozeb} = 10\% \text{ zineb} + 70\% \text{ maneb}$$

$$\text{Formulation} = 75\% \text{ mancozeb} + 25\% \text{ additives.}$$

The data obtained by both the above procedures are in good agreement. The results (Tables 2-4) show that the present method can be successfully applied for the standar-

Table 1. Comparison of analytical data

Amount taken		EDTA consumed ml	Amount of mancozeb found mg	Calculated amount (μg) of		Calculated amount of mancozeb mg	% Difference
Zn (μg)	Mn (μg)			Zineb	Maneb		
32.685	228.544	0.6	1.30	137.849	1103.576	1.241	-4.54
65.370	457.088	1.1	2.35	275.698	2207.151	2.483	+5.66
98.055	685.632	1.5	3.20	413.547	3310.727	3.724	+16.37
130.740	914.176	2.0	4.30	551.396	4414.302	4.966	+15.49
163.425	1142.72	2.4	5.15	689.245	5517.877	6.207	+20.05

Table 2. EDTA titrations with different formulations by direct method

Amount taken mg	Formul. I	Formul. II	Formul. III
	Amount found, mg/ (Error%)	Amount found, mg/ (Error%)	Amount found, mg/ (Error%)
3.75	4.80 (+28.00)	4.10 (+9.30)	4.60 (+22.70)
7.50	7.60 (+1.30)	7.20 (-4.00)	7.20 (-4.00)
11.25	11.60 (+3.10)	11.20 (-0.44)	11.40 (+1.30)
15.0	16.20 (+8.00)	14.40 (-4.00)	14.40 (-4.00)
18.75	19.90 (+6.10)	18.20 (-2.93)	18.20 (-2.93)

dization of mancozeb formulations. The initial cost as well as the operation cost of this method is lower than that of spectrophotometry³⁻⁵ and gas chromatography⁶.

Table 3. EDTA titrations with different formulations by replacement method

Amount taken mg	Formul. I	Formul. II	Formul. III
	Amount found, mg/ (Error%)	Amount found, mg/ (Error%)	Amount found, mg/ (Error%)
3.75	4.10 (+9.30)	3.60 (-4.00)	3.60 (-4.00)
7.50	6.40 (-14.70)	6.80 (-9.30)	7.00 (-6.70)
11.25	9.70 (-13.80)	11.60 (+3.10)	10.60 (-5.80)
15.00	14.00 (-6.70)	14.60 (-2.70)	14.60 (-2.70)
18.75	17.80 (-5.10)	18.90 (+0.80)	19.40 (+3.47)

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Solutions of zinc metal (0.1 M) in HCl, manganese sulphate (0.065 M) in distilled water, Eriochrome black T in triethanolamin-ethanol and ammonia buffer of pH 10 were prepared by reported procedures^{4,9}. Mancozeb suspension (1 g/100 ml) was prepared in distilled water.

Table 4. EDTA titrations with different formulations by replacement method without ascorbic acid

Amount taken mg	Formul. I	Formul. II	Formul. III
	Amount found, mg/ (Error%)	Amount found, mg/ (Error%)	Amount found, mg/ (Error%)
3.75	3.50 (-6.70)	4.30 (+14.70)	4.30 (+14.70)
7.50	7.40 (-1.30)	7.60 (+1.30)	7.00 (-6.70)
11.25	10.00 (-11.10)	11.00 (-2.20)	11.00 (-2.20)
15.00	15.40 (+2.70)	14.40 (-4.00)	13.70 (-8.70)
18.75	19.60 (+4.50)	18.60 (-0.80)	18.40 (-1.87)

EDTA titrations: For standardization of EDTA, standard zinc solution (2 ml of 0.1 M) was taken, ammonia buffer (10 ml) and indicator (1 ml) were added to it and total volume was made upto 100 ml with distilled water. The wine-red solution so obtained was titrated with EDTA solution till blue colour appeared. The standard EDTA solution was used to titrate zinc and manganese in mancozeb formulation with and without ascorbic acid by direct and replacement titrations⁹.

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